

THE ROLE OF AYURVEDIC MANAGEMENT OF AMAVATA W.S.R. TO RHUMATOID ARTHRITIS DISEASE – A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

In the current era of sedentary lifestyles, unhealthy dietary habits, and chronic stress, the incidence of *Ama*-related disorders has significantly increased. One such prevalent condition is *Amavata*, first described by *Madhavkara* in 700 A.D., which closely resembles rheumatoid arthritis (RA) in modern medicine. *Amavata* is a disease in which vitiation of *Vata Dosha* and accumulation of *Ama* take place in joint(s), and it simulates rheumatoid arthritis (RA) at modern parlance. With the limitations of modern medicine, there is a growing shift towards Ayurveda for holistic and sustainable management of *Amavata*. A 44 years female presented with pain in multiple joints associated with swelling and stiffness since 1 month was diagnosed as *Amavata*. The patient was treated with *Dashang lepa*, *Guduchi bharad Kashaya*, *Vaitarana basti*, *walukapotali*

sweda and oral medications. Contemporary medicine offers DMARDS and steroid medications for very long time as it is Auto immune condition. Whereas on other hand *Panchakarma* therapies can target on root cause of the *Vyadhi* and provide more promising results.

KEYWORDS: *Amavata*, Rheumatoid Arthritis, *Ama*, *Vata Dosha*, Autoimmune Disease, Joint Disorders, DMARDS, NSAIDs, Chronic Inflammation.

INTRODUCTION

Rheumatoid arthritis (RA) is a chronic joint disease-causing inflammation. It is symmetrical, destructive and affects small and large joints.^[1] The disease most often begins between the ages of 30 and 50, but recent observational studies indicate that the disease can begin in any age group.^[2] The worldwide prevalence of the disease is approximately 0.8% of the population.^[3] *Amavata* is a disease in which vitiation of *Vata Dosha* and accumulation of *Ama* take place in joints, which stimulate rheumatoid arthritis (RA) in modern parlance.^[4] *Ama* is a maldigested product, which is not homogeneous for the body. Whenever that *Ama* gets localized in the body tissue or joints, it can lead to production of pain, stiffness, swelling, tenderness, etc., in the related joints.^[5] The present time due to modern life style, unhealthy eating habits, hectic schedule and stress, incidence of *Ama* related diseases are increasing. One of the most common disease is *Amavata*. In Ayurveda, *Madhavkara* (700 A.D.) first mentioned *Aamvata* as a separate disease.^[6] Some symptoms resemble RA like pain, stiffness, swelling, lethargy. Ayurveda suggests preventive and curative measures, including Panchkarma radical treatment to eliminate causative factors. This study evaluates the effectiveness of Langhana, Valuka Swedana, classical Virechana Karma, classical Basti Karma, and oral Shamana Aushadhi for managing Rheumatoid Arthritis. Parvasandhi shool and Shoth, Sarva sandhi shool and shoth Katishool, Tam pravesh, Bhrhma, Ubhay hastapad chimchimayan, Daurbalya Malaavasthambh, Prusthshool, For this patient took allopathy treatment but got temporary relief, then she decided to take Ayurvedic treatment. So, for further Ayurveda treatment patient approached to L.k. Ayurvedic Hospital, Shivaji nagar, yavatmal.

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Method - Single Case Study

Material- Ayurved literature and samhita.

AIM AND OBJECTIVE

To evaluate efficacy ayurvedic Drugs in the management of a case of *Aamvata*.

Place- PG department of Kayachikitsa Laxmanrao Kalasapurkar Ayurvedic College Yavatmal, affiliated with D. M.M Ayurved college yavatmal.

A Case Report: A 44 year female patient came to OPD of kayachikitsa department With chief complaints of

1. *Sarvangsandhishool* and *shotha* (Pain over joints) since 1 month
2. *Sandhi kriyaalpata* (Restricted movement) since 1 month
3. *Dvaya pada shul and shotha* (leg pain and swelling over joint)
4. *Daurbalya*(Weakness) since 1 month
5. Morning stiffness since 1 month
6. *Agnimandya* since 1 month
7. *parvasandhi shool nd shoth*

History of present illness - Patient had a complaint of sandhishool since 1 month gradually several joints get involved and severity of pain and swelling around joints increased day by day, he had taken analgesic but with those drugs he got temporary relief. So, she come to Kaychikitsa O.P.D. of L.K. Ayurvedic hospital for further treatment.

Past History – NO H/O - DM/ HTN/Thyroid or any major illness
Known case Asthma, History of Renal calculi.

➤ Surgical History - H/O Appendectomy (2 yrs ago)

Family History - No any family history related to patient's illness.

Rugna Parikshan

Ashtavidha Parikshan

NADI-80/Min

MAL-Samyak

MUTRA - Samyak

JIVHA-Saam

SHABD Spashta

SPARSH -Samshitoshna

DRUKA- Raktshvetabha

AAKRUTI -Madhyam

GENERAL EXAMINATION

GC – Moderate

Pulse – 80/min

BP – 100/70 mm of Hg

R.R. – 18/min

Wt. – 63.80 kg

Ht – 149 cm BMI – 28.7

Lmp – 06/ 01/25

Local Examination

Swelling presents on ankle joint of right leg, both knee joints, *parvasandhi*

Tenderness presents on ankle joints of right leg, both knee joints, *parvasandhi*

Strotus - Rasahava, Asthivaha

Strotoshudhi -Sanga

Adhishtan- Sarvasandhi

Vyadhimarg-Madhyam

Koshth-Krur

Here, *Amavata* (Rheumatoid arthritis) was diagnosed on the basis of symptoms described in the classics.

Systemic Examination

CVS - S1S2 Sounds audible, No murmur sound.

CNS - Consious and Oriented.

RS - AEBE, Clear

P/A - No tenderness/soft

Investigation

Hb-10.2 gm%, WBC-10,340/cumm, Plt- 3.89 lakh/cumm

ESR - 25mm/1hr, RBC - 3.44 mil/cumm, BSL- 98 mg/dl, Sr. Uric acid-6.69 mg/dl

RA FACTOR – Negative

titre - 17 IU/ml (Sero Negative)

CRP- Positive

titre - 19.8 mg/l (positive)

ASO - titre 200 (negative)

Urine routine and microscopic

Appearances – hazy, colour - pale yellow, pus cell - 1-2 pus/H.P. F

Epithelial cell – 1-2 pus/H.P. F

Protein – absent

Sugar – absent

Treatment

1. आरोग्यवधीनी वटी 500 mg Vyanodane (BD) with koshnajal
2. सुतशेखर रस 250 mg Vyanodane (2BD)
3. गुडूची दशमुल भरड क्वाथ 30ml – 30ml Vyanodane (BD)
4. सिंहनाद गुग्गुल 500 mg Vyanodane (BD) (व्याधी प्रभाव)
5. आम वातारी रस 250 mg Vyanodane (2BD)
6. अग्नितुंडी वटी 250 mg Vyanodane (2BD)

7. दशमूळ रासना पुनर्नवा अश्वगंधा त्रिफळा 1gm each Vyanodane (BD)
8. पंचसकार चूर्ण 3gm HS
9. दशांग लेप (LA)

PANCHAKARMA CHIKITSA

10. वैतरण बस्ति - for 1st 3 days, then P. K opinion, again advice वैतरण बस्ति for next 3 days.

(गुळ, चिंचा, सेंधव- मधुर आम्लवन रस -वात शामक रस)

11. वालुका पोट्टली स्वेद - for 6 days
12. कटी बस्ति - for 6 days

DISCUSSION

- *Amavata* is mainly caused due to vitiation of *Tridosha* and formation of *Ama*. *Mandagni* is the main cause of *Ama* production. *Langhana* has been mentioned to be the best measure for the treatment of *Ama*. *Langhana* in the form of *Laghu Ahar* was advised to the patient.
- As per *Yogratnakar*, *chitiksa* siddhant of *Amavata* includes *Langhana*, *Swedana*, drugs having *Tikta*, *Katu Rasa* and *Deepana* action, *Virechana*, *Snehapana* and *Anuvasana* as well as *Ksharabasti*.
- *Rukshasweda* had been advised in the form of *Valukapottali sweda* due to the presence of *Aam*.
- *Vaitaran Basti* had been advised for 6 days.

Shaman chikitsa

After panchkarma chikitsa *shaman* drug should be administered. they can be given as single drug or compound drug. The action of drugs used in this treatment are *vaathar* and *vaatanulomak* and *aam pachak*.

Arogyavardhani Vati - It contains *abhrak bhasma*, *Tamra bhasma*, *Lohabhasma*, *Kutki* which is *pachak*, *bhedak* reducing *aam*, which ultimately works form *samprapti bhanga*.

Aamvatari Ras-Amavatari Rasa balance *Vata*, *Pitta* and *Kapha*.It helps in decreasing pain, swelling and stiffness in joints. It reduces the symptoms of *Aamvata*.

Punarnava Guggul - Punarnava guggul helps reduce the inflammation occurred due to *Vata Dosh*a and also useful to promote strength of bones and joints.It acts as an excellent anti-inflammatory, analgesic medicine and Anti-arthritis formulation which serves as a remedy for severe rheumatoid arthritis.

Vaatvidhvans ras - It contains drugs that can stimulate or reduce the action of immune system molecules in the body. so, it works for the treatment of autoimmune disease like Rheumatoid Arthritis.

Singhnad Guggul - It mainly works over joint pains, swelling, stiffness and inflammation associated with rheumatoid arthritis. Powered with castor oil which acts antirheumatic, antitoxin, antimicrobial, laxative. Guggul works *Deepana* (enhances stomach fire), *Pachana* (helps in digestion), *Amahara* (treats indigestion).

Guduchi bharad kwath - It works as a potent immunomodulator, this traditional herb holds high significance in the treatment and management of feverishness in *aamvata* and diminished immunity.

Panchasakar churn - used as *vaatanulomak* and balance *vata*.

Valuka Pottali Swada - This *ruksha sweda* has unique therapeutic effect of this procedure is *kaphahara* (beneficial in the treatment of *Kaphadosha*) and *shothashulahara* (alleviates the pain & swelling).

Vaitaran Basti - This enema is known for its effectiveness in treating *Amavata* due to the properties of its ingredients, which help to balance *Vata* and reduce *Ama*.

Majority of drugs given have *Deepan*, *Ama-Pachan*, *Shothaghna*, *Shoolghna*, *Jwaraghna*, *Balya* and *Amavatahara* properties. It enhances the *Agni-Bala* reduces the *Ama* and prevents the further *Ama* formation into the body. This reduces the clinical manifestations of *Amavata* and helps in breaking the *Samprapti* of *Amavata*.

CONCLUSION

From above discussion we can conclude that There were marked reduction in sign and symptoms of *Aamvata vyadhi*. Thus, this ayurvedic treatment can be utilised in treating patients who are suffering from *Aamvata* i.e Rheumatoid Arthritis.

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